

Timetable Generation Using Genetic Algorithm

Abhishek Scariya M B

PG Scholar

*Master of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, Kottayam, India*

abhishekscariyamb2022a@mca.ajce.in

Paulin Paul

Asst. Professor

*Master of computer Applications
Amal Jyothi college of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, Kottayam, India*

paulinepaul@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—Generating a college timetable is a hard and arduous task that requires a lot of effort from the side of teachers across departments. It requires a lot of time and patience. Although many academic institutions use software for educational and management purposes, most of them doesn't have an automated timetable generator. They still create timetables manually. Proposed work is a proposal for generating timetables using genetic algorithm without any clashes regarding teachers, courses, resources, departments and sections.

Keywords—Genetic algorithm, machine learning, timetable generation

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite the fact that the majority of university administrative work has seen digitalization, the scheduling is still done manually due to the difficulties involved. Manual programming necessitates a significant amount of time and effort. A schedule consists of allocating a certain resource to objects in time and space in order for them to achieve a set of ideal goals. The subject of the university class schedule causes us to locate some spaces and classrooms in order to adhere to the restrictions imposed on courses, professors, and classrooms, among other things. Scheduling, also known as timetabling, is the process of allocating time for scheduled activities in a systematic and orderly manner in order to achieve a good outcome with minimal limitations. This is a combinatorial optimization problem, which implies that as the number of variables increases, the computation time climbs exponentially.

II. DESCRIPTION

Most academic institutions face problems while generating a timetable that accommodates all subject classes and in order to make this task simpler, this timetable generator has been created. It has been developed with a simplified user interface that allows users ease of access and a superfast response time. It helps in managing courses, meetings, departments, teachers, sections and classrooms. The algorithm has been designed to allow automatic allocations and provides a clash-free solution to every combination.

The old method assumed that each class had one group of students, one instructor, and any number of times which could be picked at will when it came to class or instructor scheduling. Since then, the issue has been researched on a regular basis in a variety of scenarios. It was first mostly utilized in schools. Traditional approaches such as linear or integer programming may be easily implemented since the challenge in schools is relatively simple owing to the lack of complicated class structures. The problem gets increasingly

difficult when more cases of upper secondary schools and colleges with various sorts of advanced class systems are explored.

Machine learning is a subset of computer science that permits computers to learn without being explicitly programmed. One of the most exciting technologies ever found is machine learning. It gives computers the ability to learn, bringing them closer to humans. Machine learning is currently employed in a lot more places than you would expect.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning are getting a lot of traction around the world. The breadth of Artificial Intelligence's uses has changed the face of technology. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning are two terms that are occasionally used synonymously. There is, however, a key differential between the two that many industry professionals are still ignorant of.

When a computer algorithm performs intelligent work, it's observed as computer science (AI). Machine Learning, on the opposite hand, is a facet of AI that learns from data moreover as information acquired from previous experiences, allowing the pc programs to regulate its behavior accordingly. Machine Learning could be a subset of AI, hence all Machine Learning is AI, but not all AI is Machine Learning.

There are many ways to generate a timetable. Some of them being – graph coloring algorithms, mathematical programming algorithms, database management systems etc. In this case, we use genetic algorithm to solve the timetabling problem.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

Shraddha Thakare, Tejal Nikam and Prof. Mamta Patil [1] in their paper "Automated Timetable Generation using Genetic Algorithm" uses genetic algorithm to generate a college timetable by taking into various factors such as courses, programs, departments, halls etc. Timetable generated are between 60% - 80% best solution.

Mrs.G.Maneesha, T.Deepika, S.BhanuSri, N.RaviKumar and P.SivaNagamani [2] in their paper "Automatic Time Table Generation Using Genetic Algorithm" generates the timetables automatically by taking the inputs like the number of subjects, teachers, the workload of a teacher, semester, and priority of subjects.

In their paper "Genetic Algorithm for Solving University Timetabling Problem", U. M. Modibbo1, Umar, M. Mijinyawa, and R. Hafisu4 [3], they developed the

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6874378

ISBN: 978-93-5607-317-3@2022 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

selection process in such a way that the program code would need to run crossover and mutation processes in less time, raising the convergence rate of new schedules and lowering the new scheduling generation time.

Shraddha Shinde, Saraswati Gurav and Sneha karme in their paper [4] "Automatic Timetable Generation using Genetic Algorithm" will keep track of timetables when a teacher is absent or arrives late or departs early. The proposed method will assist in the automatic generation of it, as well as saving time. Faculty members do not need to be concerned about period specifics or maximum workload.

The Genetic Algorithm, according to Kehinde Wiilams and Micheal Ajinaja in their study [5], is one of the most successful methods of producing schedules, despite the fact that it does not produce a perfect timetable. The degree to which it is optimal is governed by the constraints imposed as well as the parameters' fitness function. Using Genetic Algorithm is a little slower due to the steps that must be taken. You must produce random numbers, alter, and cross over parameters before receiving the final result. In order for a Genetic Algorithm to be implemented, the constraints that will be applied must be carefully determined in order to achieve the best possible result. Regardless, it is still the most effective method for resolving scheduling challenges.

IV. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This project's main goal is to create a timetable generator that can produce accurate and reasonably sensible schedules for schools and colleges. This helps the teachers by avoiding the arduous task of manually drafting a timetable.

V. METHODOLOGY

To design a schedule, we adopt a genetic process. GAs are heuristic search algorithms with adaptive heuristics that fall under the category of evolutionary algorithms. Genetic algorithms are built on the foundations of natural selection and genetics. These are ingenious uses of random search, aided by historical data, to guide the search to a solution space area with greater performance. They're typically employed in the development of greater solutions to optimization and search issues..

Fig 1. General flowchart of genetic algorithm

Natural selection is simulated by genetic algorithms, which means that organisms that can adapt to changes in their environment will live, reproduce, and pass on to the next generation. They replicate "survival of the fittest" among individuals of successive generations with the purpose of addressing a problem. Each generation is composed of a population of individuals, each of whom represents a possible solution and a location in the search space. Each person is characterized by a string of characters, integers, floats, and bits. The Chromosome is equivalent to this string

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

We have used Django, a popular python framework for back-end. As for the front-end, HTML and CSS have been used.

Steps involved in a genetic algorithm for timetabling schedule are:-

1. Data encoding and decoding
2. Initial population
3. Evaluation of population
4. Crossover Evolution
5. Mutation
6. New Population

Data encoding and decoding: Data encoding is the initial step in the Genetic Algorithm process. It converts a solution into a chromosome in order to obtain a simple value, such as a string. It's utilized to boost the algorithm's speed. Converting the data to a binary string is a simple approach to do it. A gene is a chromosomal component that can be encoded as a binary string. The algorithm can be treated more easily when the data has been converted to this kind. Side-by-side gene strings make up the chromosomal string.

Initial population: It is the initial step in the GA process. It entails employing severe limitations to generate a large number of random individuals. The user's needs determine the

population choice. Because of evolution, a tiny population will shrink and eventually annihilate the entire population within a few generations. A huge population, on the other hand, will produce better outcomes but will demand more resources and be slower. A set can be used to represent the population.

Evaluation of population: The fitness of a solution is a soft constraint-based evaluation of how excellent it is. The solution is correct in this range. The evaluation of the population is the core of the Genetic algorithm. This stage determines which answer is superior than the others by employing a fitness feature. A range of 0 to 1 can be used to indicate fitness. If 1 is thought to be the population's best solution, other individuals are being used to range them.

Fitness Function:

$$F(X) = 1 / (1.0 * \text{number_of_conflicts} + 1)$$

The solution with a fitness of 1 is selected as the optimal solution.

Crossover Evolution: The crossover evolution method is a technique for generating a new population from an older one. Two chromosomes are used in basic crossover evolution, which allows for the creation of X new chromosomes. It entails slicing the two chromosomes into pieces and assembling new chromosomes from the pieces.

Mutation: To get the algorithm moving, mutation is used. It entails changing the values of a gene at random, resulting in a whole new and unanticipated result. These methods provide a fresh perspective on the fitness function. The mutation solely affects the chromosome and has no effect on other solutions.

New Population: Crossover and mutation allow for the creation of a new population of unique solutions.

Hard constraints:-

- Unique class timing
- Students enrolled in a course <= Seating capacity of room
- Two classes don't have same room
- Class timing for each teacher is unique
- Teachers are allocated to their course accordingly

Soft constraints:-

- Classes are allocated according to section requirements
- All courses are according to their department
- Even distribution of course in a section per week

Fig 2. Homepage UI for timetable generator

Course	Room	Teacher	Meeting Time
C1 Data Structures	RS101	T1 Karthikeyan	Wed1 Wednesday 9:30 - 10:30
C1 Data Structures	RS101	T1 Karthikeyan	Tue2 Tuesday 10:30 - 11:30
C1 Data Structures	RS101	T1 Karthikeyan	Fri4 Friday 12:30 - 1:30
C1 Data Structures	RS101	T1 Karthikeyan	Mon1 Monday 9:30 - 10:30
C1 Data Structures	RS101	T1 Karthikeyan	Wed3 Wednesday 11:30 - 12:30
C2 Software Engineering	RS101	T2 Kapil	Fri3 Friday 11:30 - 12:30
C2 Software Engineering	RS101	T2 Kapil	Thu4 Thursday 3:30 - 4:30
C2 Software Engineering	RS101	T2 Kapil	Tue6 Tuesday 11:30 - 12:30
C2 Software Engineering	RS101	T2 Kapil	Thu1 Thursday 9:30 - 10:30
C2 Software Engineering	RS101	T2 Kapil	Wed4 Wednesday 12:30 - 1:30
C3 Digital Fundamentals	RS101	T3 Nirala	Fri5 Friday 2:30 - 3:30

Fig 3. Sample output

VII. CONCLUSION

I have implemented a timetable generator using genetic algorithm in python. It does even allocation for all subjects. However, from the results obtained after continuous testing, it can be noted that due to even allocation for courses for a section, some hours may remain unallocated. A proposed way of overcoming this hurdle is by introducing a dictionary which has section_id as its key and a list of unallocated meeting_times. And use this to carefully allocate the free hours without teacher clashes.

```
free_hours = { "section_id" : [ ] }
allocate(free_hours, incomplete_schedule)
```

We can further optimize the timetable by adding subject type to distinguish between theory and lab hours for assigning separate resources (rooms) and introducing continuous lab hours.

VIII. REFERENCES

[1] Shraddha Thakare, Tejal Nikam and Prof. Mamta Patil, "Automated Timetable Generation using Genetic Algorithm"; (IJERTV9IS070568)

[2] Mrs.G.Maneesha, T.Deepika, S.BhanuSri, N.RaviKumar and P.SivaNagamani "Automatic Time Table Generation Using Genetic Algorithm"; (JETIR2107265)

- [3] U. M. Modibbo1 , Umar, M. Mijinyawa and R. Hafisu4 “Genetic Algorithm for Solving University Timetabling Problem”
- [4] Shraddha Shinde, Saraswati Gurav and Sneha Karne “Automatic Timetable Generation using Genetic Algorithm”
- [5] Kehinde Wiilams and Micheal Ajinaja “Automatic Timetable Generation Using Genetic Algorithm”